

A NEW INTEGRATED ANISOMORPHIC CFL DIAGRAM APPROACH TO OFF-AXIS FATIGUE LIFE PREDICTION OF CFRP LAMINATES AT ANY TEMPERATURES IN ANY FIBER-ORIENTATIONS

M. Kawai^{*}, Y. Kumazawa, H. Udo

Department of Engineering Mechanics and Energy,
University of Tsukuba, Tsukuba, Japan

* Corresponding author (mkawai@kz.tsukuba.ac.jp)

Keywords: *Polymer matrix composite, fatigue, Off-axis loading, Temperature dependence, Anisomorphic constant life diagram, S-N curve prediction*

1 Introduction

Not only spectrum and orientation of fatigue loading but also temperature at which fatigue load is sustained by composite structures during service are usually different in each application. Doing constant amplitude fatigue tests at different stress ratios and temperatures in different fiber orientations that might be involved by loading of CFRP structures during service requires a lot of time and cost. For CFRP laminates that feature any stacking configuration tailored adapting for application, it is obviously inefficient to rely all on experiments for identification of their S-N relationships under different fatigue loading conditions. For efficient fatigue analysis of structural components made of CFRP, therefore, it is required to establish a fatigue life prediction method that enables us to accurately and efficiently predict their fatigue lives (S-N curves) for any fiber orientations of CFRP that is subjected to fatigue load over a wide range of stress ratio and temperature on the basis of a set of reference data for selected loading conditions.

One of the most practical methods for efficiently predicting the S-N relationships for composites for constant amplitude fatigue loading for any stress ratio at a given temperature is to use a constant fatigue life (CFL) diagram [1]. A CFL diagram consists of the envelopes for different constant values of life that are typically drawn in the plane of alternating stress and mean stress. Once a CFL diagram for a given composite laminate is constructed, it allows graphically evaluating a fatigue life under constant amplitude fatigue loading at any stress ratio. Because of its practical importance, attention is increasingly focused on identification of the CFL diagrams for CFRP laminates over the whole range of mean stress.

The experimental observations have encouraged developing an engineering method suitable for composites that allows describing the CFL diagrams for composites efficiently as well as accurately, which are asymmetric and nonlinear in general, over the whole range of mean stress. Mandell et al. [2] and Sutherland and Mandell [3] presented modified Goodman diagrams that were built assuming linear interpolation of fatigue data at different stress ratios. Harris et al. [4-6] have attempted a systematic study on identification of the CFL diagrams for CFRP laminates, and found that the CFL envelopes for those composites can adequately be described by means of a bell-shape function, regardless of the kinds of fibers and matrices. It is the first attempt to develop an engineering model that allows analytically describing both the overall asymmetry and the overall nonlinearity in the CFL diagrams and thus S-N curves for composites over the whole range of stress ratio. Because of its potential usefulness, the bell-shape CFL method should further be tested on different types of CFRP laminates for different fatigue loading conditions.

Taking account of the change in shape of CFL envelope with increasing value of life, in addition to ease of construction of the CFL diagrams for composites, Kawai [7] and Kawai and Koizumi [8] have recently proposed a new and efficient method, called the anisomorphic CFL diagram approach, for describing the asymmetric and nonlinear CFL diagram for a given composite laminate by using only the reference S-N curve for a particular stress ratio and the static strengths in tension and compression. The use of fatigue data for the particular stress ratio, called the critical stress ratio, which is given by the ratio of compressive strength to tensile strength is a distinguishing feature of the anisomorphic CFL diagram approach.

The accuracy of prediction using the anisomorphic CFL diagram approach turns inaccurate in case of a large change in mean stress sensitivity that results in a significantly distorted and inclined shape of CFL diagram, as observed by Kawai and Murata [9] for symmetric angle-ply CFRP laminates. This problem can be removed using a modified anisomorphic CFL diagram that is constructed with the help of the additional reference fatigue data for an auxiliary stress ratio as well as the fatigue data for the critical stress ratio, although it needs a little more fatigue data that should be obtained from experiments. It is thus suggested that the anisomorphic CFL diagram approach has a potential for fatigue analysis of composite not only for fiber-dominated fatigue but also for matrix-dominated fatigue.

The present study aims to establish an integrated anisomorphic CFL diagram based fatigue life prediction methodology for composites that takes into account the effects of three parameters, i.e. stress ratio, fiber orientation and temperature. A particular emphasis is placed on further testing of the anisomorphic CFL diagram approach for its applicability to prediction of the matrix-dominated fatigue life of multidirectional CFRP laminates under off-axis loading conditions at different temperatures. Namely, it is an attempt to formulate a new engineering fatigue model on a laminate level that can efficiently predict the fatigue life of CFRP laminates under off-axis fatigue loading in any fiber orientation with any stress ratio at any temperature.

2 Experiment Procedure

2.1 Material and Specimens

Carbon/epoxy, symmetric, alternating, cross-ply laminates fabricated from the prepreg tape T700S/2592 (TORAY) were used in this study. The lay-up of the laminate is $[0/90]_{3S}$. Three kinds of coupon specimens with different fiber orientations $[\theta/-(90-\theta)]_{3S}$ ($\theta = 0^\circ, 15^\circ$ and 45°) were prepared.

2.2 Test Procedure

On- and off-axis fatigue tests were performed at room temperature (RT) and high temperatures of 70°C and 90°C under load control. Fatigue load was applied in a sinusoidal waveform with a frequency of 5 Hz. The values of stress ratio R of fatigue loading were specified as $R = 0.1, \chi, -1$ and 10 , where R designates the ratio of minimum fatigue stress (σ_{\min}) to maximum fatigue stress (σ_{\max}); i.e. $R = \sigma_{\min} / \sigma_{\max}$. A particular value of stress ratio, χ , which is called the critical stress ratio [7], is defined as $\chi \equiv \sigma_c / \sigma_T < 0$ in which $\sigma_c (< 0)$ and $\sigma_T (> 0)$

denote the compressive and tensile strengths for each fiber orientation at each temperature.

3 Experimental Results

3.1 Temperature dependence of off-axis static strength

The effects of temperature on off-axis tensile strength of the cross-ply CFRP laminate that were observed for different fiber orientations $\theta = 0^\circ, 15^\circ$ and 45° are shown in Figs. 1(a), (b) and (c), respectively. As seen in Fig. 1(a), the reduction in tensile strength with temperature in the fiber direction is small even at the highest test temperature of 90°C , indicating a low sensitivity to temperature in the longitudinal tensile strength. For the off-axis fiber orientations ($\theta = 15^\circ$ and 45°), on the other hand, more significant reduction in tensile strength with increasing temperature can be observed over the range of temperature.

Similarly, a low sensitivity to temperature in compressive strength in the fiber direction and a high sensitivity to temperature in compressive strength in off-axis fiber directions were observed in the range up to 70°C as well.

3.2 Stress-ratio dependence of off-axis S-N relationship

For the representative fiber orientation $\theta = 45^\circ$, the off-axis fatigue data at room temperature for different stress ratios $R = 0.1, \chi (= -0.66)$ and 10 are shown in Fig. 2, as plots of the maximum fatigue stress σ_{\max} for T-T loading and T-C loading and the minimum fatigue stress $|\sigma_{\min}|$ for C-C loading against the number of reversals to failure $2N_f$ on the linear and log scales. The off-axis static strengths in tension (UTS) and compression (UCS) are plotted at $2N_f = 1$ as points of the ordinate in the S-N diagram.

From Fig. 2, it is seen that the dashed lines fitted to the fatigue data extrapolate back to the tensile strength in the case of T-T ($R = 0.1$) and T-C ($R = \chi$) fatigue loading, and to the compressive strength in the case of C-C fatigue loading ($R = 10$). The average slope of the S-N relationship for C-C loading at $R = 10$ is milder than that for T-T loading at $R = 0.1$, showing that the relative fatigue strength, i.e. the fatigue strength relative to the reference static strength (UCS for $R = 10$ and UTS for $R = 0.1$), becomes higher under C-C loading. Obviously, the fatigue lives for loading at the critical stress ratio $R = \chi = -0.66$ are much shorter than the fatigue lives

(a) $\theta = 0^\circ$

(b) $\theta = 15^\circ$

(c) $\theta = 45^\circ$

Fig. 1 Temperature dependence of off-axis tensile strength

for $R = 0.1$ and 10 . It is also seen that the slope of the S-N relationship for the critical stress ratio is likely to be steeper than the slopes of the S-N relationships for $R = 0.1$ and 10 . These facts suggest

Fig. 2 Off-axis S-N curves for different stress ratios at room temperature ($\theta = 45^\circ$)

Fig. 3 Off-axis S-N curves for different fiber orientations at room temperature ($R = 0.1$)

that the sensitivity to fatigue in the off-axis direction $\theta = 45^\circ$ of the cross-ply laminate becomes highest under T-C fatigue loading at a stress ratio in the vicinity of the critical stress ratio. In fact, it has been observed that most rapid degradation in quasi-isotropic and cross-ply CFRP laminates occurs under T-C fatigue loading at the critical stress ratio [8].

3.3 Fiber-orientation dependence of off-axis S-N relationship

Fig. 3 shows comparison of the off-axis S-N relationships for different fiber orientations $\theta = 0^\circ$, 15° and 45° that were obtained from room temperature fatigue tests at a constant stress ratio $R = 0.1$. It is seen that there is a significant difference in maximum stress level between the off-axis S-N

Fig. 4 Normalized off-axis S-N curves at room temperature ($R = 0.1$)

Fig. 6 Normalized off-axis S-N curves at different temperature ($R = 0.1$, $\theta = 45^\circ$)

Fig. 5 Off-axis S-N curves at room temperature ($R = 0.1$, $\theta = 45^\circ$)

relationships for different fiber orientations, corresponding to the difference in off-axis static tensile strength.

The off-axis S-N data for loading at $R = 0.1$ in the fiber orientations $\theta = 0^\circ$, 15° and 45° that were presented in Fig. 3 are normalized with respect to the off-axis static strengths observed, and they are plotted in Fig. 4 against the number of reversals to failure. Overall, the difference between the off-axis S-N relationships for different fiber orientations can almost be removed by the normalization of fatigue stress. Observing the results in more detail, however, we can see that the normalized off-axis fatigue data for $\theta = 15^\circ$ and 45° are likely to be more closely distributed at a level slightly off the level of the normalized fatigue data for $\theta = 0^\circ$. A similar feature

was observed in the normalized S-N relationships for the other stress ratios.

For the cross-ply laminate tested in this study, therefore, it is suggested that the fatigue strength ratio is a useful measure for analysis of the off-axis fatigue data, but two normalized master S-N curves, instead of a single curve, should be identified for fatigue loading in the on-axis and off-axis directions, respectively, to cope with the fiber orientation dependence of the off-axis fatigue data.

3.4 Temperature dependence of off-axis S-N relationship

Fig. 5 shows comparison of the off-axis S-N relationships at different temperatures $T = RT$ and $70^\circ C$ that were obtained from fatigue tests at a constant stress ratio $R = 0.1$ using coupon specimens with $\theta = 45^\circ$. It appears that the off-axis S-N relationships obtained for the given fiber orientation at different temperatures are almost in parallel with each other. This suggests that the difference between the S-N relationships is comparable to the difference between the static strengths at these different temperatures, and thus the reduction in off-axis fatigue strength with increasing temperature is similar to that in off-axis static strength.

These observations reveal that the difference between the off-axis S-N relationships for a given stress ratio at different temperatures can approximately be removed by normalization of maximum fatigue stresses with respect to tensile strengths at the same temperatures, as demonstrated in Fig. 6.

From these observations, therefore, it is suggested that the fatigue strength ratio can be conveniently used to identify the normalized master S-N relationships that are insensitive to fiber orientation as well as temperature for on-axis and off-axis fatigue loading conditions, respectively.

4. Anisomorphic CFL diagram for off-axis fatigue of composites

The anisomorphic CFL diagram for composites [7, 8] can be constructed following the procedure of this approach for off-axis fatigue loading as well. Namely, once the tensile and compressive strengths and the S-N relationship for a critical stress ratio, which is given by the ratio of the compressive strength to tensile strength, are identified at a given temperature in a given fiber orientation, a two-segment anisomorphic CFL diagram [7, 8] can be built using them.

In case of insufficient accuracy of prediction of S-N relationships using the two-segment anisomorphic CFL diagram constructed, it may be upgraded to a generalized anisomorphic CFL diagram, either a three-segment version [9] or a four-segment version [10], that makes use of additional fatigue data at auxiliary stress ratios that are different from the critical stress ratio, by which the accuracy of prediction of S-N curve as well as that of CFL diagram can be enhanced.

4.1 Four-segment anisomorphic CFL diagram

In the general four-segment anisomorphic CFL diagram [10], the right and left transitional segments are defined as $[\chi, \chi_R] = \{R : -\infty < \chi \leq R \leq \chi_R \leq 0\}$ and $[\chi_L, \chi] = \{R : -\infty \leq \chi_L \leq R \leq \chi < 0\}$, respectively, using two auxiliary stress ratios χ_L and χ_R in conjunction with the critical stress ratio χ which is equal to the ratio of compressive strength σ_c (< 0) to tensile one σ_T (> 0), i.e. $\chi = \sigma_c / \sigma_T \in (-\infty, 0)$. The right and left auxiliary stress ratios χ_R and χ_L are determined so as to satisfy the condition $-\infty \leq \chi_L \leq \chi \leq \chi_R \leq 0$. The total interval of mean stress $[\sigma_c, \sigma_T]$ is thus separated into four subintervals: I. $[\sigma_m^{(\chi_R)}, \sigma_T]$; II. $[\sigma_m^{(\chi)}, \sigma_m^{(\chi_R)}]$; III. $[\sigma_m^{(\chi_L)}, \sigma_m^{(\chi)}]$; IV. $[\sigma_c, \sigma_m^{(\chi_L)}]$. The CFL envelopes on these subintervals are described in the alternating stress σ_a versus mean stress σ_m plane by means of the following piecewise-defined functions:

[I] Tension-dominated zone ($\sigma_m^{(\chi_R)} \leq \sigma_m \leq \sigma_T$):

$$-\frac{\sigma_a - \sigma_a^{(\chi_R)}}{\sigma_a^{(\chi_R)}} = \left(\frac{\sigma_m - \sigma_m^{(\chi_R)}}{\sigma_T - \sigma_m^{(\chi_R)}} \right)^{2-\psi_{\chi_R}^{k_T}} \tag{1}$$

[II] Right transitional zone ($\sigma_m^{(\chi)} \leq \sigma_m < \sigma_m^{(\chi_R)}$):

$$-\frac{\sigma_a - \sigma_a^{(\chi_R)}}{\sigma_a^{(\chi_R)} - \sigma_a^{(\chi)}} = \frac{\sigma_m - \sigma_m^{(\chi_R)}}{\sigma_m^{(\chi)} - \sigma_m^{(\chi_R)}} \tag{2}$$

[III] Left transitional zone ($\sigma_m^{(\chi_L)} \leq \sigma_m < \sigma_m^{(\chi)}$):

$$-\frac{\sigma_a - \sigma_a^{(\chi)}}{\sigma_a^{(\chi)} - \sigma_a^{(\chi_L)}} = \frac{\sigma_m - \sigma_m^{(\chi)}}{\sigma_m^{(\chi_L)} - \sigma_m^{(\chi)}} \tag{3}$$

[IV] Compression-dominated zone ($\sigma_c \leq \sigma_m < \sigma_m^{(\chi_L)}$):

$$-\frac{\sigma_a - \sigma_a^{(\chi_L)}}{\sigma_a^{(\chi_L)}} = \left(\frac{\sigma_m - \sigma_m^{(\chi_L)}}{\sigma_c - \sigma_m^{(\chi_L)}} \right)^{2-\psi_{\chi_L}^{k_C}} \tag{4}$$

where $\sigma_a^{(\chi)}$ and $\sigma_m^{(\chi)}$ are the alternating stress and mean stress components of the maximum fatigue stress $\sigma_{\max}^{(\chi)}$ for fatigue loading at the critical stress ratio $R = \chi$; i.e.

$$\sigma_a^{(\chi)} = \frac{1}{2}(1 - \chi)\sigma_{\max}^{(\chi)} \tag{5}$$

$$\sigma_m^{(\chi)} = \frac{1}{2}(1 + \chi)\sigma_{\max}^{(\chi)} \tag{6}$$

Similarly, $\sigma_a^{(\chi_R)}$ and $\sigma_m^{(\chi_R)}$ represent the coordinates for the right auxiliary stress ratio $R = \chi_R$, and $\sigma_a^{(\chi_L)}$ and $\sigma_m^{(\chi_L)}$ are the coordinates for the left auxiliary stress ratio $R = \chi_L$. The fatigue strength ratios ψ_{χ} , ψ_{χ_R} and ψ_{χ_L} associated with the critical stress ratio and the right and left auxiliary stress ratios, χ_R and χ_L , are defined as

$$\psi_{\chi} = \frac{\sigma_{\max}^{(\chi)}}{\sigma_T} \tag{7}$$

$$\psi_{\chi_R} = \frac{\sigma_{\max}^{(\chi_R)}}{\sigma_T} \tag{8}$$

$$\psi_{\chi_L} = \frac{\sigma_{\min}^{(\chi_L)}}{\sigma_c} \tag{9}$$

In order to calculate the fatigue strengths for a given number of cycles for loading at the critical and auxiliary stress ratios, we need to identify the S-N curves for those stress ratios:

(a) $\theta = 0^\circ$

(b) $\theta = 15^\circ$

(c) $\theta = 45^\circ$

Fig. 7 Off-axis anisomorphic CFL diagrams at 70°C

$$2N_f^{(\chi)} = f(\psi_\chi) \quad (10)$$

$$2N_f^{(\chi_R)} = f(\psi_{\chi_R}) \quad (11)$$

$$2N_f^{(\chi_L)} = f(\psi_{\chi_L}) \quad (12)$$

These reference S-N curves can conveniently be described by means of the following function:

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{K^*} \frac{1}{x^n} \frac{\langle 1-x \rangle^a}{\langle x-x_{(L)} \rangle^b} \quad (13)$$

where the angular brackets $\langle \cdot \rangle$ indicate a singular function defined as $\langle x \rangle = \max\{0, x\} = (x + |x|) / 2$.

4.2 Applicability of 4-segment anisomorphic CFL diagram

The four-segment anisomorphic CFL diagrams for fatigue loading in the directions $\theta = 0^\circ, 15^\circ$ and 45° at room temperature are shown in Figs. 7(a), (b) and (c), respectively. It is seen that the four-segment anisomorphic CFL diagram approach succeeds in accurately describing the nonlinear and asymmetric CFL diagram of the cross-ply CFRP laminate not only for loading in the fiber direction but also for loading in the off-axis directions. These observations demonstrate that the four-segment anisomorphic CFL diagram approach is applicable to off-axis fatigue failure at 70°C and 90°C as well.

A complete verification of the four-segment model requires more data at different stress ratios, since the fatigue data for $R = 0.1$ and 10 were used to identify the CFL diagrams and thus the accuracy of prediction was verified only for $R = -1$ in this study. In view of a smooth transition between fatigue behaviors at different stress ratios in the four segments, nevertheless, it is believed that the four-segment anisomorphic CFL diagram captures the overall shape of a CFL diagram for the cross-ply CFRP laminate in any off-axis fiber orientation, and thus it offers a potential for adequately predicting the S-N curves for any stress ratios at which no fatigue data are available.

5. Integrated CFL-based fatigue life prediction methodology for composites in any fiber orientation at any temperature

A phenomenological model that can predict the fatigue lives of orthotropic composites for any off-axis orientation at any constant temperature in a specified range is formulated on a laminate level by means of a generalized version of the fatigue damage mechanics approach [11].

5.1 Off-axis master S-N relationship

The evolution of a scalar variable ω that represents the magnitude of fatigue damage under on-axis and off-axis fatigue loading at a specified constant temperature is described by means of the following differential equation of a general form:

$$\frac{d\omega}{dN} = Kh(\Pi^*) \left(\frac{1}{1-\omega} \right)^k \frac{\langle \Pi^* - \Pi_L^* \rangle^m}{\langle 1 - \Pi^* \rangle^c} \quad (14)$$

where Π^* designates either the non-dimensional effective stress σ^* [11] or the modified non-dimensional effective stress Σ^* [12], and thus it takes a value in the range $0 \leq \Pi^* \leq 1$. Hereafter Π^* is called the generalized non-dimensional effective stress. The coefficients K, k, n, a and b and Π_L^* are material constants, and $h(\Pi^*)$ is a function of Π^* . For constant amplitude off-axis fatigue loading, Eq. (14) yields the following master S-N relationship:

$$N_f = \frac{1}{(1+k)K} \frac{1}{h(\Pi^*)} \frac{\langle 1 - \Pi^* \rangle^\ell}{\langle \Pi^* - \Pi_L^* \rangle^m} \quad (15)$$

5.2 Off-axis grand master S-N relationship

For coping with the effect of temperature on fatigue life from an engineering point of view, it is convenient to assume scaling of fatigue life by means of a temperature-life parameter.

One of the commonly used time-temperature parameters (TTPs) is the Larson-Miller (LM) parameter P_{LM} for creep rupture [13]. By analogy, the LM parameter for fatigue $P_{LM}^{(F)}$ is defined as

$$P_{LM}^{(F)} = T(F + \log N_f) \quad (16)$$

where T is temperature in K, N_f is the number of cycles to failure, F is a material constant that gives a shift along life axis; F is called the LM constant for fatigue in this study.

If fatigue data at different temperatures that are plotted using the theoretical fatigue strength ratio and the LM parameter for fatigue are closely distributed to each other, they can be represented by a master S-N curve of the form:

$$P_{LM}^{(F)} = \frac{1}{(1+k)K} \frac{1}{h(\Pi^*)} \frac{\langle 1 - \Pi^* \rangle^\ell}{\langle \Pi^* - \Pi_L^* \rangle^m} \quad (17)$$

The master S-N curve can be identified by fitting this function to the plots of normalized stress and shifted fatigue life over a range of temperature. Note that the static failure condition $\Pi^* = 1$ corresponds to $P_{LM}^{(F)} = 0$, suggesting that the static strength data are to be plotted at the equivalent life of $N_f = 10^{-F}$.

The function $h(\Pi^*)$ involved by the expression of a grand master S-N curve may be specified in terms of a hyperbolic function

$$h(\Pi^*) = [\sinh(\alpha \Pi^*)]^n \quad (18)$$

where α is an additional material constant

(a) CFL diagram

(b) S-N curves

Fig. 8 Predicted anisomorphic CFL diagram and S-N curves for $\theta = 0^\circ$ at 70°C

that should be determined by fitting to data.

5.3 Identification of a grand master S-N relationship for off-axis fatigue

A method to define a single grand master S-N curve for fatigue loading at any stress ratio has not been established yet, to the best of the authors' knowledge. For a few given stress ratios, however, it is possible to approximately identify the associated grand master S-N curve. It is thus suggested that using the grand master S-N curves identified for loading at the critical stress ratio and the auxiliary stress ratios, we can construct a four-segment anisomorphic CFL diagram for any temperature in any fiber orientation. In the present study, we develop an integrated fatigue life prediction methodology along this line. Namely, three grand master S-N curves that are independent of fiber orientation as well as temperature over an assumed range of temperature are first identified for T-T fatigue loading at $R = 0$,

(a) CFL diagram

(a) CFL diagram

(b) S-N curves

(b) S-N curves

Fig. 9 Predicted anisomorphic CFL diagram and S-N curves for $\theta = 15^\circ$ at 70°C

Fig. 10 Predicted anisomorphic CFL diagram and S-N curves for $\theta = 45^\circ$ at 70°C

C-C fatigue loading at $R = \infty$, and T-C fatigue loading at the critical stress ratio $R = \chi$. Then, the standard four-segment anisomorphic CFL diagram [10] is constructed for each of given fiber orientations at each of specified temperatures by means of those grand master S-N curves.

5.3.1 The grand master S-N curve for T-T loading at $R = 0$

For T-T fatigue loading at the constant stress ratio $R = 0$, the generalized non-dimensional effective stress Π^* may be considered as the non-dimensional effective stress σ_{\max}^* :

$$\Pi^* = \sigma_{\max}^* = \Omega_T(\theta, T) \sigma_{\max} \quad (19)$$

where

$$\Omega_T(\theta, T) = \sqrt{\frac{m^4}{X_T(T)^2} - \frac{m^2 n^2}{X_T(T)^2} + \frac{n^4}{Y_T(T)^2} + \frac{m^2 n^2}{S_T(T)^2}} \quad (20)$$

5.3.2 The grand master S-N curve for T-T loading at $R = \infty$

In the case of off-axis C-C fatigue loading, the generalized non-dimensional effective stress can be identified with the theoretical fatigue strength ratio associated with minimum fatigue stress. It can thus be written as

$$\Pi^* = \sigma_{\min}^* = \Omega_C(\theta, T) |\sigma_{\min}| \quad (21)$$

where

$$\Omega_C(\theta, T) = \sqrt{\frac{m^4}{X_C(T)^2} - \frac{m^2 n^2}{X_C(T)^2} + \frac{n^4}{Y_C(T)^2} + \frac{m^2 n^2}{S_C(T)^2}} \quad (22)$$

5.3.3 The grand master S-N curve for T-C loading at $R = \chi$

In the case of off-axis T-C fatigue loading at critical stress ratio, the generalized non-dimensional

effective stress can be considered as the modified theoretical fatigue strength ratio

$$\Pi^* = \Sigma_\chi^* \tag{23}$$

where the modified non-dimensional effective stress for critical stress ratio is given as

$$\Sigma_\chi^* = \begin{cases} \frac{\sigma_a^{*(\chi)}}{1 - \sigma_m^{*(\chi)}}, & -1 \leq \chi < 0 \\ \frac{\sigma_a^{*(\chi)}}{1 + \sigma_m^{*(\chi)}}, & -\infty < \chi \leq -1 \end{cases} \tag{24}$$

The non-dimensional alternating stress σ_a^* and mean stress σ_m^* can be defined, respectively, as

$$\sigma_a^* = \sigma_a \begin{cases} \Omega_T(\theta), & 0 \leq \sigma_m \leq \sigma_T \\ \Omega_C(\theta), & -|\sigma_c| \leq \sigma_m < 0 \end{cases} \tag{25}$$

$$\sigma_m^* = \sigma_m \begin{cases} \Omega_T(\theta, T), & 0 \leq \sigma_m \leq \sigma_T \\ \Omega_C(\theta, T), & -|\sigma_c| \leq \sigma_m < 0 \end{cases} \tag{26}$$

where σ_a and σ_m represent alternating stress and mean stress components, respectively.

5.4 Comparison with experiment results

The predicted off-axis anisomorphic CFL diagrams for different fiber orientations $\theta = 0^\circ, 15^\circ$ and 45° at 70°C are shown in Figs. 8, 9 and 10, respectively, together with the predicted off-axis S-N curves for different stress ratios. For the fiber orientations $\theta = 0^\circ$ and 45° , it is seen that good predictions have been obtained for all the stress ratios tested in this study, including the stress ratio $R = -1$ for verification. For the fiber orientation $\theta = 15^\circ$, however, slightly conservative predictions have been obtained for all the stress ratios except for C-C loading at $R = 10$.

It may be thus concluded that the integrated CFL based fatigue life prediction methodology developed in this study has succeeded in adequately predicting the off-axis S-N relationships in different fiber orientations at different temperatures for the complexity of the problem that involves the two parameters of fiber orientation and temperature. Since the fatigue data for $R = \chi, 0.1$ and 10 were used for identification of the associated grand master S-N curves, the integrated methodology proposed in this study, strictly speaking, was verified only for the case of $R = -1$. In order to fully verify the integrated CFL based fatigue life prediction methodology developed in this study, therefore, we

need to compare predicted and experimental results for different fatigue loading conditions that are not used for identification.

6. Conclusions

A new engineering fatigue life prediction methodology for efficiently predicting the off-axis S-N relationship for an arbitrary stress ratio at an arbitrary temperature using the anisomorphic CFL diagram was developed. To achieve this purpose, two models are established. One of the two models is for accurately predicting the off-axis strengths in tension and compression for arbitrary fiber orientation at arbitrary temperature. Another one is for predicting the reference S-N curve for the off-axis critical stress ratio that depends on temperature as well as fiber orientation.

These two tool models, the modified Tsai-Hill failure criterion with consideration of temperature dependence and the normalized grand master S-N curve approach for the off-axis critical stress ratio that varies with temperature and fiber orientation, are combined with the anisomorphic CFL diagram approach to be integrated into a unified fatigue life prediction methodology that allows predicting the off-axis S-N relationship of CFRP laminates for fatigue loading at any stress ratio and temperature in any fiber orientation.

The off-axis S-N relationships for cross-ply CFRP laminates that were predicted for fatigue loading at different temperatures, in different fiber orientations, at different stress ratios by using the integrated fatigue model developed in this study were shown to agree well with experimental results, demonstrating a potential of the anisomorphic CFL diagram based integrated fatigue model for fatigue life analysis of composites.

Acknowledgement

The authors gratefully acknowledge the support of research grants from the Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology of Japan under a Grant-in-Aid for Scientific Research (No. 25289002) and the TANIKAWA Foundation for Thermal Technology.

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